

ONTOLOGY-FIRST DATA MODEL DESIGN FOR CROSS- DOMAIN ANALYSES

Eugenio Salvador Arellano Ruiz, Fabia Miorelli, Niklas Wulff, Carsten Hoyer-Klick,
Patrick Jochem

This presentation © 2024 by German Aerospace Center (DLR),
Institute of Networked Energy Systems, Department of Energy
Systems Analysis is licensed under CC BY 4.0

Abstract

Publishing data aligned with the FAIR principles requires discipline specific efforts. This presents particularly complex challenges when dealing with interdisciplinary contexts.

Research on existing and projected charging infrastructure is data intensive and existing publications, although open to the principles of open and transparent science, lack soundness in their data publications which compromises their reproducibility.

In this work we analysed profoundly the interoperability of charging infrastructure data. We do this by implementing our interpretation of the FAIR principles in existing open infrastructure data. Using this data we propose different data models that can be used in diverse operational and research contexts.

We validate these models in two ways, the first is systematic and in line with the ontology development process of asking and answering competency questions. The second is a hands-on reproduction of existing open data research. This work sets the theoretical basis to justify the creation of an ontology for the mobility and transport sectors that enable interoperability with the energy sector.

The FAIR principles, going beyond open data.

iScience

CellPress
OPEN ACCESS

Open Research Europe

Open Research Europe 2022, 1:156 Last updated: 15 JUN 2023

Article

Analysis of electric vehicle charging station usage and profitability in Germany based on empirical data

Christopher Hecht, Jan Figgenger, Dirk Uwe Sauer

batteries@isea.rwth-aachen.de

Highlights
Usage analysis of 22,000 German public charging stations

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.105634>

RESEARCH ARTICLE

REVISED Modelling charge profiles of electric vehicles based on charges data [version 3; peer review: 2 approved]

Nataschia Andrenacci , Federico Karagulian , Antonino Genovese

Ente per le Nuove Tecnologie, l'Energia e l'Ambiente (ENEA), Rome, 00193, Italy

v3 **First published:** 23 Dec 2021, 1:156
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14354.1>
Second version: 14 Feb 2022, 1:156
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14354.2>
Latest published: 25 May 2022, 1:156
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14354.3>

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

1 2

<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14354.3>

THE DATA FIRST APPROACH

German Federal Network Agency (BNetzA) data context

The regulation on charging infrastructure (Ladesäulenverordnung, LSV)

- First published in 2016
- Rules the technical requirements of a safe and interoperable expansion of the battery electric vehicle charging infrastructure in Germany.
- The Ladesäuleregister is published in its context.

<https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/lsv/>

The German public charging column register (Ladesäuleregister)

- Public Charging station operators must report their stations to the BNetzA.
- These operators can consent to have their infrastructure openly published in the website of the agency.
- This means that there is an unknown amount of open charging points that might not be published openly.
- It is updated at irregular intervals, older versions are always superseded by the newest one.

<https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de>

A detailed evaluation of the German public charging column register published data

- Data is provided as a MS Excel workbook. Alternatively, a csv exported from MS Excel is provided. The latter has the same information in the former but is prone to errors, so is better to use the workbook.
- The dataset has multiple formatting issues
 - The encoding is not explicitly stated, we figured out that it is ISO 8859-1.
 - Numerical columns had mixed data types.
 - Float numbers in the same column were using different decimal separators.
 - Some empty cells were using white spaces leading to processing issues.
 - The headers were multileveled so manual changes were needed to convert into proper CSV.
- Some entries were seemingly duplicated. But it could also be the case that the operator submitted them like that.
- Validating the whole dataset is beyond the scope of this work but by validating some random entries we confidently assure that the duplication is most likely an error.
- Is not evident that the data is archived upon change. When a new version of the registry is uploaded is not clear that older versions can be accessed.

Ladesäulenregister Bundesnetzagentur

Hinweis:

Die Liste beinhaltet die Ladeeinrichtungen aller Betreiberinnen und Betreiber, die das Anzeigeverfahren der Bundesnetzagentur zum Zeitpunkt der Aktualisierung vollständig abgeschlossen und einer Veröffentlichung im Internet zugestimmt haben. Die Zahl der öffentlich zugänglichen Ladeeinrichtungen in Deutschland ist daher größer als hier dargestellt.

Letzte Aktualisierung vom: 12.12.2023

Allgemeine Informationen													
Betreiber	↓ Straße	↓ usnum	↓ Adresszus.	↓ Postle	↓ Ort	↓ Bundesland	↓ Kreis/kreisfreie St.	↓ Breitengrad	↓ Längengra	↓ Inbetriebnahm	↓ Nennleist	↓ Art der Ladeei	↓ Anzahl Ladepu

FAIRification of public charging infrastructure data

FAIRification is a neologism that describes the process of making data and processes FAIR.

We make the dataset FAIR through five measures:

- **Cleaning** the data ensuring Interoperability
- Providing structured metadata **Annotations** making it **Findable** by machine agents
- **Normalising** allowing Interoperability with database systems.
- **Translating** some terms to English to make it available to a wider audience.
- **Validating** against the metadata standards
- Versioning and **Publishing** in the Open Energy Platform to ensure its **Accessability**, even after a new version of the registry is released.

To ensure **Reusability** the metadata points clearly to the license. Although the original is being licensed, finding the license is not straight forward as the website has to be navigated*.

The code containing all the steps reported in this presentation can be found in GitHub at:

<https://github.com/areleu/fair-charging-station-data>

FAIRification - Cleaning

- The cleaning of the data was performed by solving the formatting issues associated mainly with numerical columns
- We ensured that the column “Anzahl Ladepunkte” accounted properly for the number of entries in the charging point columns.
- What we suspect are duplicated columns were dropped. In the provided script this is optional.

Charging columns found at the address Aralalle 1 in Thüringen. From the BNetz data one could infer that there are four charging columns, but the public map information points to only two of them. Source: OpenStreetMap

FAIRification – Annotation

- Metadata of the original dataset is spread across the publishing website.
- By using a structured specification we ease the machine actionability of the data.
- The Open Energy Family (OEF) provides with a metadata specification called the Open Energy Metadata which is an extension of the frictionless data package specification adjusted to support semantic annotation.
- To add semantics to the data we use several vocabularies like the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) by the OEF and the Core Location Vocabulary (LOCN) by the European Commission.

<https://github.com/SEMICeu/Core-Location-Vocabulary>

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/ontology/>

FRictionless
STANDARDS

<https://specs.frictionlessdata.io/data-package/>

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata/>

FAIRification – Normalisation and Translation

FAIRification – Normalisation and Translation

Tables are separated and associated with keys

FAIRification – Normalisation and Translation

Arrows represent foreign key relationships

FAIRification – Validation and Publishing

- The metadata specification is supplemented by a json schema. This allows easy validation of the metadata using open libraries.
- The data is then published in two repositories.
- First in the Open Energy Platform which only supports single table models.

<https://openenergy-platform.org>

- To publish the normalised dataset we use Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10362445>

- Zenodo provides the data a DOI which allows the clear identification of the dataset, it also offers a way to archive older version. This enables Accessibility.

ONTOLOGY FIRST?

Data driven RDF Graph models

- As a further progression of the work presented in the previous section. We propose using the emerging data model as a basis to build a graph.
- This by assigning each table an entity type with their fields as attributes and their foreign keys as relations.
- RDF graphs can profit from existing vocabularies, we use multiple existing ontologies alongside a placeholder ontology in this work

Ontology/Vocabulary	Scope
Open Energy Ontology (OEO)	Power capacity
The Core Location Vocabulary (LOCN)	Location information
Electric Vehicle Graph (EVG)	Placeholder vocabulary for BEV related facts.

The shortcomings of data driven interoperability

- Until now we have only dealt with counter-examples of ontology first design.
- Even the graph model relies on existing data structures.
- Shortcomings of this approach:
 - Data interoperability is achieved only after significant effort. When this is done by someone different than the original authors, semantics are subject to interpretation.
 - Knowledge bases become a product of concatenating often incompatible models coming from experts of specific subfields of a discipline. (Silo Problem)
 - Knowledge engineering takes a secondary role, data models are **Emerging**.

Emerging data model

An emerging data model is such that is produced as an artefact of a process.

Context driven data models

- To achieve self-explanatory datasets that are FAIR from its conception, **guidelines, policy and infrastructure** have to be part of the production process. In such process, model requirements and the evaluation of such are a must.
- Evaluating data models is not easy and very context specific.
- Metadata is the structured consolidation of said context.
- Ontology-first means to define context before producing data and metadata.
- In the world of ontology development is often talked about “Competency questions”. These are queries that are to be stated and answered by their associated ontology.
- We can derive a parallel for data models intended to be shared within a community.

Ontology First

Ontologies First Means

- To begin data model design by asking the questions the data is intended to answer.
- To consider the tentative scopes of interest based on a target audience
- Exploring existing ontologies for the terminology needed if any. Or declare statements of need by formally describing the terminology as part of the publication.
- If the second option is picked, always rely first on existing scientific consensus, if there is not one then add terminology as a definition with axioms and try to justify it in the context of your work.
- Add context first, which means to write metadata before anything.
- Draft model schemas that follow the defined terminological scope.
- Prefer data structures that can be programmatically queried.
- Validate your model by converting the questions defined at the beginning into queries and comparing with expected output

Defining the conceptual scopes and strive towards consensus

Example queries

- What is the maximum charging capacity at city X?
- What is the maximum connection power at city X?
- What is the total installed AC (or DC) capacity at city X?
- What are the total amount of available AC (or DC) connections at city X?
- How many AC (or DC) charging columns were commissioned per year Y?

Data has many forms

- Just like we as humans have many languages and ways of communicating, computer systems rely often in multiple data structures and protocols. So the multiplicity of data structures should not be ignored when considering interoperability.
- Not all data structures can be systematically queried
- For example, lets look at different ways of asking “What is the maximum charging capacity at city X?”

Different ways of asking “What is the maximum charging capacity in X city?” (Spreadsheet software)

1. Add a new spreadsheet

2. Go to Insert > Pivot Table

3. Select your dataset

Different ways of asking “What is the maximum charging capacity in X city?” (Spreadsheet software)

4. Click on the filters that you want to apply

5. Find your results in your spreadsheet

Zeilenbeschriftungen	capacity
Kreisfreie Stadt Hamburg	63086,55
Kreisfreie Stadt Berlin	51337,95
Landkreis Region Hannover	41870,91
Landkreis Böblingen	34945,5
Stadtkreis Stuttgart	32183,8
Kreisfreie Stadt München	26972,7
Kreisfreie Stadt Düsseldorf	26597,65
Landkreis München	26591,9
Kreis Mettmann	23100,85
Kreisfreie Stadt Köln	22763,25
Kreisfreie Stadt Dresden	22003
Landkreis Heilbronn	21885,75
Kreisfreie Stadt Wolfsburg	21311,47
Kreis Unna	20679,95

Different ways of asking “What is the maximum charging capacity at city X?”


```
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX evg: <https://www.evgraph.de/>
PREFIX locn: <http://www.w3.org/ns/locn#>
PREFIX oeo: <http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

SELECT ?au (SUM(?capacity) AS ?cap) WHERE {
  ?s oeo:OEO_00140002 ?cp.
  ?cp oeo:OEO_00140178 ?capacity.
  {
    SELECT ?s ?au WHERE {
      ?s rdf:type oeo:OEO_00320040;
        locn:location ?l.
        ?l locn:address ?a.
        ?a locn:adminUnitL2 ?au.
    }
  }
}
GROUP BY ?au
ORDER BY (?cap)
```

SPARQL

```
import frictionless as fl

DATAPACKAGE = "oep_normal/bnetza_charging_stations_normalised_01_02_2023.json"
METADATA = "metadata/metadata_v152.json"

COLUMN_RESOURCE = "bnetza_charging_columns_01_02_2023"
LOCATION_RESOURCE = "bnetza_locations_01_02_2023"
OPERATOR_RESOURCE = "bnetza_operators_01_02_2023"

# Use frictionless to extract pandas (game changer)
package = fl.Package(source=DATAPACKAGE, profile=METADATA)
columns = package.get_resource(COLUMN_RESOURCE).to_pandas()
locations = package.get_resource(LOCATION_RESOURCE).to_pandas()

# Actual pandas query
charging_capacities = (
  columns.join(locations, how="left", on="location_id")
  .groupby(["county"])
  .aggregate({"net_capacity": sum, "charger_amount": "mean"})
  .sort_values("net_capacity")
)
```

Python with Pandas

```
SELECT county, SUM(net_capacity) AS capacity
FROM bnetza_charging_columns_01_02_2023 AS columns
LEFT JOIN bnetza_locations_01_02_2023 AS locations
ON columns.location_id = locations.id
GROUP BY county
ORDER BY capacity
```

SQL